

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Mengnjo**FIRST NAME:** Fonyuy Francis**PROGRAM CODE:** DCCS**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

COURSE 401D QUIZ QUESTIONS AND MODEL ANSWERS

1. What is plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information with full citation and referencing on where the information is from.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- It is not considered plagiarism when you call the writer and ask for his permission to use his peace of work in your dissertation and do not reference or cite the person.
- In general, there is nothing like plagiarism, so use any information at your disposal freely and with acknowledgment.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

2. What citation style does Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* documents use?
- ACA.
 - APA Citation Style.
 - Chicago/Turabian Citation Style.²**
 - MLA Citation Style.
3. What are the two common citation forms covered in Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*?
- Notes-bibliography style, or simply notes style and author-date style.³**
(Together, these two styles are often referred to as the Turabian or Chicago systems of source citation).
 - Author date style and Citation referencing.
 - Author page number style and bibliography style.
 - Simple note style and intext quotation note style.
4. Thesis (pl. Theses) is a long-form document presenting an argument and research evidence. What is 'research'?
- A hypothesis within the thesis.
 - The Introduction to the Thesis.

² Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*: Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago press, 2018), 147.

³ Ibid., 141.

- Answering a question by obtaining information. In this sense, research can be as simple as choosing a new phone or as complex as discovering the origin of life.⁴**
- The conclusion to the Thesis.
5. Conducting dissertation research involves preparing two to four documents. Which of the components of Dissertation research used?
- Dissertation manuscript.
- The Introduction, body and conclusion.
- The whole dissertation format of the presentation.
- Dissertation concept Paper, Dissertation prospectus, Dissertation, Dissertation manuscript.⁵**
6. Which of the below is the reason for a research bias when conducting research or writing a dissertation?
- Selecting specific variables, measures, treatments, participants, and data analyses that increases the chances of obtaining specific predetermined findings.
- Selectively emphasizing specific sources from the literature review in the discussion of the findings.
- Selectively emphasizing specific discussion points in the implications section.

⁴ Ibid., 19.

⁵ James P. Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research: Second Edition* (Florida State University, 2017), 9.

- Selecting specific variables, measures, treatments, participants, and data analyses that increases the chances of obtaining specific predetermined findings.
- All of the above.**⁶
7. What are the various sources of potential bias in dissertation research work or thesis (Choose the most accurate answer)?
- Policy bias and Theory bias.
- Experience bias, population bias, theory bias, intervention bias, funding bias and policy bias.**⁷
- Intervention bias.
- None of the above is suitable.
8. What do you understand as a statement of the problem during dissertation writing?
- Is a statement of problem with the actual problem to address the dissertation objective.
- It is a statement that identifies why the research is being taken.
- Justification of the research.
- The statement of the problem is a succinct statement of the dilemma that the research questions are intended to resolve and should provide a clear rationale for the research questions.**⁸

⁶ Ibid., 15.

⁷ Ibid., 15.

⁸ Ibid., 35.

9. What do you understand as a style guide in dissertation, thesis or research writing (choose the most accurate answer)?

- It is just writing that follows a particular style or procedures to make it readable and understandable.
- It is like designing a house to suit your taste and ensuring that all the objectives are made.
- It is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to some aspects of your writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting.⁹**
- All of the above is correct and should be considered as the right options.

10. In data collection, researchers can decide to use multiple methods of data collection in a single dissertation to ensure that essential and accurate data is being captured. What is this method of data collection called?

- Triangulation method.¹⁰**
- Sampling method.
- Multiple data collection sources method.
- Accurate method and data collection.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 41.

¹⁰ Bloomberg, Linda, and Volpe Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. 4th Edition (Thousand Oaks, Colombia University, 2019), 452.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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